

NanoPAT Newsletter

December 2023

Online real-time characterisation solutions for
nanoparticle production processes

#07

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Welcome

Dear reader,

The NanoPAT project is glad to present our **seventh newsletter** aiming to communicate our latest technical achievements, introduce our innovative partners and share inputs and curiosities related to nanotechnology and process monitoring.

In this seventh issue you will find an update of the project status. Furthermore, two of NanoPAT's project partners will be presented and our achievements of the last months will be highlighted!

NanoPAT is currently running its fourth and final year. So far we are very satisfied with the progress made by all partners. In a technical aspect, all the three technologies have been successfully validated in the laboratory by our research organisations and we are in the phase of pilot scale validation incorporating the PAT systems into the lines of the five demonstrators participating in the project.

On the other hand, our monitoring system is in its last phase of development and soon will be ready to communicate with all the PAT systems

and other devices in the industrial field. As a last step, a further processing of data will take place using data fusion AI algorithms.

If you are interested in the evolution of NanoPAT activities, coming from an academic, industry, or other perspective, and would like to closely follow the progress of the project and its outcomes, do not hesitate to contact us on nanopat_coordination@iris.cat and subscribe to our [newsletter](#) to receive further information and explore possible collaborations.

Best regards and enjoy the read,

Poojan Timilsina,
Coordinator of NanoPAT

Project status

Since our last newsletter ([issue #6 - May 2023](#)), and thanks to a hardworking team, there have been plenty of activities within the NanoPAT project within the last 6 months.

In July 2023 the whole consortium met to organise our **Review Meeting 2** as well as our **General Assembly (M38)** in Athens (Greece) at the facilities of our colleagues from Cnano. It was a great get-together with lots of very

fruitful discussions and getting up-to-date with the developments and achievements during the last months, which set the basis for the next and final month. Special thanks Project Officer and Evaluator for their valuable suggestions and their support in encouraging our continued progress!

NanoPAT partners during the General Assembly hosted by Cnano in their facilities in Athens.

Several **Safe-by-Design activities** have been performed in the last months, from a risk assessment perspective, where TEMASOL and BNN have analysed the facilities and processes of some of the partners (BRAVE, Fluidinova, Cnano) to identify potential health issues, relevant for the commercially fully exploitable innovative NanoPAT technologies

During the last months, and after the validation at lab-scale of NanoPAT process analytical technologies (PATs), the installation of the sensor at the pilot plants has partially taken place. With this, we have entered the phase of the **industrial implementation of the three PATs** (PDW, OF2i and TUS) in each one of the case studies (OF2i and TUS at Cnano - Ceramics case study, OF2i at Fluidinova - Hydroxyapatite case study, PDW at Evonik - Silica case study), performing trials of the sensors at the end users' facilities and demonstrating the technologies in an industrial environment. Further implementations are planned for the upcoming months.

The Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) analysis of the 5 Case Studies is running as planned to correctly place the PATs in the respective case studies and help understand the phenomenology of the different nanomaterials creation in the respective case studies. Additionally, the Digital platform will include a calculator to show velocity results and particle distribution. The calculator will include the results of some parametric studies for key scenario parameters for each of the Case Studies.

The **PATBox platform** that will store, manage and share the data produced by the PATs is

Overview of roles of the partners in NanoPAT

under development. Integration tests with the sensor technologies have been performed. At Cnano, integration with OF2i and TUS sensors were performed demonstrating the platform functionality. Other platform integration tests were performed at UPV to verify interconnection between TUS and PDW sensors. Further tests will follow in the upcoming months. Also a new functionality is being integrated in the platform, the Decision Support System. The tool will make use of the CFD analysis to provide several simulation outputs for each of the respective case studies.

Several activities have been pushed and carried out by BNN and TEMASOL towards **collaboration with other EU funded projects** with a similar or supplementary focus. Additionally, activities related to standardisation of the NanoPAT

technologies as well as its exploitation have been performed by TEMASOL, BNN and EXEL.

Moreover, the project partners have been very active with the organisation and/or participation in conferences and other events to promote their research, as well as internal knowledge transfer activities for exchanging ideas within the consortium.

Furthermore, all **public training materials and publications** that have been produced by the project and its partners until now, are now available on the project website.

Finally, the project has released two more **peer-reviewed scientific publications** with the results of the research on OF2i and TUS technologies.

You can find more details about all these activities in the upcoming sections.

Partner presentations

In this issue, we present the NanoPAT partners, Arkema & Cnano

About Arkema

Arkema is a global leader in Specialty Materials serving major societal and ecological challenges. Arkema designs materials to address the ever-growing demand for innovative and sustainable materials, driven by the challenges of new energies, new technologies, the depletion of resources, mobility, and increasing urbanisation.

Arkema has a strong expertise in zeolite synthesis and characterization. Arkema owns 2 plants producing a broad range of zeolites (in terms of zeolite structures and particle size distributions and morphologies), several pilot plant facilities and dedicated teams in the Lacq R&D Center. Arkema is involved in process intensification processes, especially for zeolite synthesis, and looks for techniques to measure particle size distribution and morphologies in real-time and process control strategies to tune very finely particle size distribution in the production lines.

Arkema supports the developments of Photon Wave Density Spectroscopy (PDW), providing reference materials, contributing to define analytical reference methods and synthesis

Arkema is able to implement and test the developed techniques for Zeolite Particle Size Measurement at different scales, from the small batch reactors (less than 1 L) to pilot plant reactors (40 L to more than 1 m³).

Cécile Lutz

Head of Molecular Sieves and Zeolites R&D

About Cnano

Creative Nano is a research intensive SME specialising in surface treatment and nanotechnology. The company has developed significant expertise in the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) pilot-scale production of nano-enabled products such as nanocomposite coatings, photocatalytic paints and biobased nanoparticles. Cnano recently moved to a fully renovated 500 m² building, comprising offices, fully equipped chemistry laboratories, electroplating pilot lines and advanced analytical facilities for the characterisation of nanomaterials and metal coatings (SEM-EDS, PXRD, DLS, Vickers hardness tester, etc).

Cnano is currently investigating the pilot-scale production of Ni-based nanocomposite coatings reinforced with ceramic nanoparticles, aiming to replace state-of-the-art “Hard Chromium” coatings whose production requires the use

of highly toxic and environmentally malign Cr(VI) chemical compounds. The Ni-based nanocomposite coatings developed in the framework of NanoPAT show excellent corrosion resistance and high hardness, comparable with Hard Chromium. Importantly, these two key properties are significantly increased when the ceramic nanoparticles are homogeneously dispersed in the Ni metal matrix. To this end, Cnano is testing in its in-house pilot-scale electroplating lines, two of the NanoPAT novel technologies, namely OptoFluidic Force Induction (OF2i) and Turbidity Spectrometry (TUS) for the real-time monitoring of the ceramic nanoparticles size and distribution to enable and on-line quality control.

Alexis Grigoropoulos

R&D manager, Nanomaterials

Alexandros Zoikis

Karathanasis

CEO, Electroplating

www.creativenano.gr

Highlights

Standardisation Workshop

On 23 October 2023, our colleagues from BNN organised a Standardisation Workshop for NanoPAT’s technology developers, to get an overview of the meaning of standardisation, how it can be used and how NanoPAT and its partners can standardise their technologies.

The aim of the workshop was to hear an overall introduction to standardisation by Dr. Denis Koltsov (Director of BREC Solutions, Limited and chair of ISO TC229 (Nanotechnologies)) and to present NanoPAT technologies. A joint discussion about the impact of a standardised technology / service will be held between

Dr. Kolstov and NanoPAT technology developers.

The workshop was hosted at the BNN office in Graz and counted, online and on-site, with all technology providers (PDWA, BRAVE, IRIS) plus TEMASOL, as leader of the project task on standardisation.

Special thanks to Denis Koltsov, who came to Graz especially for this occasion and enriched us with his knowledge and experience.

On 24 October, Denis Koltsov visited BRAVE facilities to get a better overview about the OF2i technology, in theory and in praxis, with a lab-tour and being able to see the B-continuous (B1-PAT device) and

NanoPAT featured at external newsletters / webpages

the B-curious (B2-Lab device) in real life. NanoPATs activities were published and promoted via the [BNN QUARTERLY 02/2023](#) (June 2023) and at the [innoFSPEC website](#).

Training materials & publications at NanoPAT website

All public training materials and publications that have been produced by the project and its partners until now, are now available on the [project website](#), organised in 8 different categories: marketing material (flyers, brochures, videos, presentations, etc.), reports, conference materials (presentations, posters), standardisation material, peer-reviewed publications, articles in scientific magazines, articles in newsletters, and manuals. Key information is attached to each material, e.g. title, short description, producer, DOI (if available), date of creation, as-

Recent publications

As a result of the hard work of our project partners **BRAVE Analytics** and **Medical University Graz** in the past months, a peer-reviewed scientific publication with the title “Optofluidic force induction as a process analytical technology” was released in July 2023 on the journal *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry*.

Similarly, in September 2023, the [scientific publication](#) entitled “Wavelength exponent based calibration for turbidity spectroscopy: Monitoring the particle size during emulsion polymerization reactions”, from **UPV/POLYMAT** and **IRIS** colleagues, was published in the *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*.

Moreover, in the June and August 2023 editions of the Wiley Analytical Science Magazine „GIT Labor-Fachzeitschrift“, there were 2 articles of our colleagues from **MUG** and **BRAVE** (in German and English respectively) summarising the principle of operation of OF2i for the characterisation of nanoparticles in real-time. Additionally, in the HTS magazine „Botenstoff Special on Microfluidics“ there was an article of **BRAVE Analytics** on the use of microfluidics in the technology developed by **BRAVE Analytics**.

2nd place at Wiley Analytical Science Award 2024

We are very happy to announce that the BRAVE's nanoparticle analyser, **BRAVE B-Curious**, has been awarded second place in the category „Separation, Lab Automation & Lab Equipment“ at Wiley Analytical Science Award 2024!! Congratulations to the whole team! Keep up the good work!!

Beloved colleague left NanoPat

Unfortunately, Dr. Anika Krause, a valued member of the NanoPAT team, is required to step down from her position due to personal reasons. As a representative of the [University of Potsdam \(UP\)](#), she played an important role in sustaining the Scientific & Technical (S&T) Management of the NanoPAT project, for instance by organising regular S&T committee meetings. The comprehensive overview of the project progress she gained from this greatly benefited the project officers. Anika supported them in several management tasks, particularly when a new project officer was introduced to the team.

As a UP representative, Anika also took an active role in coordinating the activities of Work Package 6 (Industrial Pilot Plant Demonstration), including the organisation of several measurement campaigns at Covestro, Evonik, Arkema and Fluidinova. Additionally, Anika made significant contributions to the project by coordinating WP2 (Photon Density Wave Spectroscopy Development) as a representative of NanoPAT partner PDWA.

We are sad to see Anika leave, thank her for her remarkable support across the entire project and wish her all the best for the future!

Anika's parting words to the NanoPAT community and its supporters:

“I enjoyed working on the NanoPAT project from the first day on. The project's Consortium, comprised of accomplished researchers, highly skilled technology developers, and experienced industrial manufacturers, forms an ideal blend of knowledge to translate innovative process analytical technologies into real industrial applications.

Beyond the impressive scientific quality, I highly appreciated the friendly and collaborative atmosphere within the project and the fantastic cooperation between so many European countries.

I am a great supporter of European research projects as they not only foster scientific growth but also facilitate social and cultural exchange within the EU.

Dear colleagues and friends from the NanoPAT project, I wish you a pleasant and successful completion of the project. Keep up the great team spirit! I hope our paths will cross again soon. Perhaps in another Horizon Europe project?"

NanoPAT News

Several visits between **NanoPAT partners** were performed during the last six months, with the main objective of networking and **internal knowledge transfer activities** to ease the developments within the projects in the upcoming months.

- In June 2023, **PDWA/UP** colleagues visited the labs of our industrial partner **Evonik** in Wessling (Germany) to conduct a PDW measuring campaign to test the technology in their reactors. Read more about it [here](#).
- In July 2023, **BNN**'s team visited **BRAVE** facilities in Graz: BRAVE gave a demonstration of their OF2i technology to BNN colleagues to facilitate the (nano)safety assessment of their processes, aligned with the work carried out in the task "Nanosafety assessment & elaboration of safety/Safety by Design guidelines". Read more about it [here](#).
- Also in July 2023, **IRIS**, **BNN** and **TEMASOL** visited **Cnano** labs, aligned with the NanoPAT General Assembly hosted by Cnano at their facilities in Athens (Greece). IRIS installed the TUS equipment and tested it at lab scale in Cnano; additionally, Cnano gave a demonstration of their processes to BNN and TEMASOL colleagues to facilitate the (nano)safety assessment of their processes. Moreover IRIS and BRAVE gave a live demonstration of their technologies (TUS and OF2i respectively) to the whole consortium, demonstrating the benefits of inline and online monitoring of nanoparticles during the production of nanocomposite coatings at Cnano's electroplating lines. Furthermore, the colleagues of IRIS performed a live demo of the PAT platform, which already integrates the TUS and OF2i characterisation technologies. Read more about it [here](#).
- In September 2023, **BRAVE** transferred their OF2i sensor to **Fluidinova**'s facilities in Porto (Portugal) and installed their OF2i B-Continuous prototype at Fluidinova's hydroxyapatite production site. Read more about it [here](#).
- In October 2023, the colleagues from **UP/PDWA** again visited **Evonik**'s labs to perform a 2nd measuring campaign, this time in a larger reaction vessel. Read more about it [here](#).
- Also in October 2023, Blanca Suarez, from **TEMASOL**, visited **Fluidinova**'s facilities in Porto (Portugal) for analysing their production processes from a Safe-by-Design (SbD)/risk

assessment perspective, to identify potential health issues, relevant for the commercially fully exploitable innovative NanoPAT technologies. Read more about it [here](#).

→ As part of a new case study (outside the project plans) testing the OF2i technology developed in NanoPAT with polymers, Usue Aspiazu, from **UPV/POLYMAT**, is visiting our colleagues from **BRAVE** for a few months (7 October 2023 - 18 March 2024). Read more about it [here](#).

Some impressions

PDW measuring campaign at Evonik

Visit of BNN at BRAVE

NanoPAT's 2nd Review Meeting & M38 General Assembly

Visit of BRAVE at FLUIDINOVA

Visit of BRAVE at FLUIDINOVA

Visit of BRAVE at FLUIDINOVA

PDW 2nd Measuring Campaign at Evonik

PDW 2nd Measuring Campaign at Evonik

Visit of TEMASOL at FLUIDINOVA

Additionally, one **External Training & Knowledge Transfer activity** was carried out to increase the commercial potential of the technologies being developed within NanoPAT. As already reported in the “Highlights” section, BNN organised a **Standardisation Workshop** with one of the gurus in this topic, Dr. Denis Koltsov (Director of BREC Solutions, Limited and chair of ISO TC229 (Nanotechnologies)).

The workshop was addressed to NanoPAT technology developers, to get an overview of the meaning of standardisation, how it can be used and how NanoPAT and its partners can standardise their technologies.

NanoPAT partners during the Standardisation Workshop organised by BNN.

NanoPAT Retrospect

During the last six months, NanoPAT was very active participating in different **conferences and events**, sharing the developments of our project and our know-how:

- On 18-23 June 2023, colleagues from UPV/POLYMAT participate at **International Polymer Colloids Conference (IPCG2023)** (Ontario, Canada) presenting a poster on the benefits and limitations of Inline monitoring of emulsion polymerization processes by Photon Density Wave (PDW) Spectroscopy. Read more [here](#).
- Colleagues from BNN, UP and Evonik attended the **6th EU-Asia Dialogue** (Berlin, Germany) on 21 June 2023, as one of the key events for standardisation activities and S(S)bD topics, as well as to get more information on regulatory trends. Read more [here](#).
- NanoPAT participated at the **14th International Workshop on Polymer Reaction Engineering (PRE2023)** (5-8 Sept 2023, Potsdam, Germany) to show some of the results of our work with polymers and PATs: particle size monitoring techniques can be very useful in the emulsion polymerization field, due to the effect that the particle size and the particle size distribution has in the final applications of the latex. UPV/POLYMAT team presented a poster and gave a flash presentation on the potentiality of Turbidity Spectroscopy (TUS) to online monitor the particle size of the polyacrylate latexes.. Read more [here](#).
- Right after the PRE 2023, the UPV/POLYMAT team participated at the **11th PhD student Workshop in PRE (WPPRE 2023 - Working Party on Polymer Reaction Engineering)** (8-10 Sept 2023, Potsdam, Germany), giving gave a talk about the monitoring of the particle size of polyacrylate latexes during seeded semibatch emulsion polymerization processes by simultaneous analysis with inline PDW and online TUS technologies. Read more [here](#).
- Our colleague Vitan Strasser, from BRAVE Analytics, attended the largest Swiss trade fair for international laboratory, measurement and automation technology in chemistry, the **ILMAC 2023** (26-28 Sept 2023, Basel, Switzerland). He gave a talk on OF2i technology, highlighting several real use cases, commenting on the benefits for the users and how OF2i technology can support global biotech and nanopollutant players. Additionally, on BRAVE's booth, Vitan was able to network with a number of interesting companies. Read more [here](#).
- Our colleagues of BNN represented NanoPAT at the **European Researchers' Night** in Graz (Austria) with a booth about Nanomaterials and Nanotechnologies with information and interactive games, as well as experiments for lots of people interested in science and new advancements. Read more about it [here](#).

- NanoPAT couldn't miss the very first edition of the **BioTech Summit Austria** (12-13 Oct 2023, Graz, Austria). BRAVE Analytics gave a pitch on OF2i technology' benefits to biotech and pharma companies, highlighting how OF2i can improve work routines and results. Additionally, BRAVE was able to meet very interesting companies for further businesses in their booth at the summit. Read more about it here.
- Our new colleague João Ameixa, from UP/innoFSPEC, gave an invited keynote talk at the **LITES 2023** in Istanbul (Turkey) (30 Oct - 1 Nov. 2023). Read more about it here.
- Our colleagues of BRAVE were able to make several contacts with biotech companies attending the **ISPPP 2023**, where BRAVE had an oral presentation and had a booth. Read more about it here.

Some impressions

NanoPAT @ EU-Asia Dialogue

NanoPAT @ PRE2023

NanoPAT @ ILMAC 2023

European Researchers' Night 2023

NanoPAT @ BioTech Summit Austria 2023

NanoPAT @ ISPPP 2023

Upcoming Events

Before we head into the Christmas break, some highlights of the events where NanoPAT will be present in the upcoming months:

- [ANTHOS 2024](#), 4-7 March 2024, Vienna (Austria)
- [Polymers 2024](#), 28-31 March 2024, Athens (Greece)
- [Analytica 2024](#), 9-12 April 2024, Munich (Germany)

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